

Studies on Some Polydentate Ligands-II

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Copper(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes of two newly synthesised sexadentate ligands have been prepared and characterised by magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral measurements.

WE have recently reported¹ synthesis and characterisation of two new sexadentate ligands, viz. 1,2-di-(*o*-1-methyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenylthio)ethane and 1,2-di-(*o*-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenylthio)ethane and their chelates with some bivalent transition metal ions. In the present communication we report the results of similar investigations on the oxygen analogues of the above thio-ligands, i.e. 1,2-di-(*o*-1-methyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenoxy)ethane (DMTPE, 1a) and 1,2-di-(*o*-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenoxy)ethane, (DETPE, 1b).

Experimental

Preparation of ligands: The two ligands were synthesised by coupling the appropriate diazonium salts and substituted hydroxylamine in an acetate buffer at 0°, and as described by Bamberger^{2,3}, Sogani and Bhattacharya⁴. Details of the preparations are described below.

1,2-di-(*o*-1-methyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenoxy)ethane (DMTPE): 1,2-Di-(*o*-aminophenoxy)ethane⁵ and substituted hydroxylamine⁶ were prepared as reported in the literature. 1,2-Di-(*o*-aminophenoxy)ethane hydrochloride (10 g) was taken in 33% hydrochloric acid (20 ml in 40 ml H₂O) and diazotised by sodium nitrite (15.0 g) in 20 ml of water. The temperature of the solution was maintained at 0-5°. The diazonium salt solution was added to *N*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (11.2 g) in 500 ml water (cooled to 0°) with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at 3-5 by the slow addition of sodium acetate solution (70 g in 200 ml H₂O). The solution was further stirred for 10 min. DMTPE separated out as a yellow coloured precipitate, which was filtered, washed with water, crystallised from ethanol and dried over anhydrous silica gel in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 193°.

1,2-Di-(*o*-1-ethyltriazene-1-oxide-3-phenoxy)ethane (DETPE): The compound was prepared by the above method using *N*-ethylhydroxylamine hydrochloride in place of *N*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride. DETPE was obtained as a pale straw-coloured crystalline compound, m.p. 124°.

Preparation of complexes:

Cobalt(II) complexes: Aqueous solution of cobalt(II) acetate and ethanolic solution of the respective ligand were mixed together in 1:1 molar ratio. The content were refluxed for ~1 h and then concentrated and cooled to obtain the crystalline complexes.

Nickel(II) complexes: pH of the ethanolic solution of the respective ligand was raised by adding equimolar amount of sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was then mixed with aqueous solution of nickel(II) acetate in 1:1 molar ratio. On refluxing the contents, the complexes precipitated out.

Copper(II) complexes: The copper(II) complexes were precipitated out instantaneously after mixing the aqueous solution of copper(II) acetate and ethanolic solution of the respective ligand in 1:1 molar ratio. In all the cases, precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in an electric oven at 60°.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra were taken in KBr pellet and in chloroform on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard and frequencies were measured by the side-band technique. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance, using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant ($\chi_g = 16.46 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs). The diamagnetic corrections for the ligand atoms and cations were computed using Pascal's constants.

Results and Discussion

Two tautomeric forms (a) and (b) are possible for both DMTPE and DETPE. Nmr and ir spectra, discussed later, are suggestive of the (b) form as predominant species for both of them.

Nmr spectra of the two ligands have been recorded in CDCl₃. The observed signals and their tentative assignments are given in Table 1. Low field signal (9.1 and 9.0) is of the correct intensity to represent the N-H protons and confirms the existence of the ligands in (b) form. It has been

(a)
1a R=CH₃

(b)
1b R=C₆H₅

shown⁷⁻¹³ that the triazene-1-oxide data favour structure (b) for such ligands.

TABLE 1

Compd.	Group	Chemical shifts τ
DMTPE	NCH ₃	5.98
	OH ₂ -CH ₃	5.48
	C ₆ H ₄ (aromatic protons)	2.60-2.90
	NH	9.10
DETPE	NCH ₂ CH ₃	8.43 (triplet)
	NCH ₂ CH ₃	5.76 (quartet)
	CH ₂ -CH ₃	5.45
	C ₆ H ₄	2.80-2.90
	NH	9.00

Infrared spectra of both the ligands exhibit strong absorption at $\sim 3340\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH). Chakravorty *et al.*⁷ have confirmed this assignment by deuterating the compounds and subsequently noting the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}/\nu_{\text{N-D}}$ ratio.

All the metal complexes have 1:1, metal:ligand composition (Table 2). The triazene-1-oxide group is known to act as bidentate⁷⁻¹³. The coordinating ability of the etherial oxygens of the ligands is also well documented⁵. The present two ligands may thus, be presumed to act as sexadentate giving six-coordinate octahedral complexes in all the cases.

Room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 2. The copper(II) complexes show normal magnetic moments for one unpaired spin along with some orbital contribution. Nickel(II) complex of DMTPE also gives normal value for octahedral nickel(II), but the value for the corresponding DETPE complex is slightly lower, which may be attributed to its polymeric nature, as also indicated from its comparatively lower solubility in organic solvents. The cobalt DMTPE complex also shows normal magnetic moment of a six-coordinate high-spin octahedral complex. But the magnetic moment of the cobalt(II)-DETPE complex is subnormal. Polymeric nature of the complex as also suggested in the case of nickel(II)-DETPE complex may be the possible reason. Since the value is intermediate between those of high-spin ($S=3/2$, ${}^4T_{1g}$, 5.20 B.M.) and low-spin ($S=1/2$, 2E_g , 1.86 B.M.), an equilibrium between the two spin states may be an alternative interpretation. Susceptibility measurements at different temperatures may solve this enigma.

The visible spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in chloroform solutions except for the nickel(II) complexes for which DMF solutions were used. The ligands showed strong absorptions in the uv region with a shoulder at

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA

Complex	Formula	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Magnetic moments B.M.
					C	H	N	
DMTPE	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆	Yellow	193	360 (352)	53.3 (53.0)	5.6 (5.6)	23.3 (23.8)	diamag.
DETPE	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆	Pale-straw	124	388 (377)	55.7 (55.1)	6.2 (6.1)	21.6 (20.9)	diamag.
Co(DMTPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ Co	Reddish-brown	239	416.9 (292.1)	46.1 (46.7)	4.3 (4.5)	20.2 (19.9)	5.20
Co(DETPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Co	Red	234	(444.9)* 48.6	(49.1) 48.6	(4.8) 4.9	(19.4) 18.9	4.25
Ni(DMTPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ Ni	Orange	232	416.7 (410.3)	46.1 (45.8)	4.3 (4.2)	20.1 (19.7)	2.99
Ni(DETPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Ni	Dull-red	218	(444.7)* 48.6	(48.2) 45.7	(4.7) 4.3	(19.1) 19.9	2.77
Cu(DMTPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ Cu	Brown	205	421.5 (407.2)	45.7 (45.0)	4.3 (4.3)	19.9 (20.3)	1.89
Cu(DETPE-2H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Cu	Brown	201	(449.5)* 48.0	(48.4) 48.0	(4.5) 4.9	(18.9) 18.7	1.83

* Could not be determined due to limited solubility in organic solvents.

$\sim 22200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. No d-d bands could be resolved in the case of the cobalt(II) complexes. Copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes, however, showed bands corresponding to octahedral geometry. The two nickel(II) complexes show identical spectra with two bands each at 8650 and 1500 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transition ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, respectively before the strong charge transfer absorption sets in. The copper(II) complexes show characteristic broad absorptions centred around 12500 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$.

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